

Artificial Intelligence for Disease Diagnosis – the Criterion Standard Challenge

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Acronyms and abbreviations (list all that are used in paper with their spell-outs)

Acronyms:

AI, artificial intelligence; CADe, computer-aided detection; CADx, computer-aided diagnosis

1 **Figure legend.**
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3 **Figure 1.** Concept of the semi-supervised learning for endoscopic images with uncertain
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5 pathological diagnoses. Unlabelled data (images without reliable pathological diagnoses) are
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7 automatically classified into clusters with use of the information obtained from labelled data (images
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9 with reliable pathological diagnoses) and similarity of the images between each data.
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3 Artificial intelligence (AI) for disease diagnosis is a hot topic. Recent studies have shown
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5 that AI tools for computer-aided detection (CADe) of polyps during colonoscopy
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9 increases the adenoma detection rate from 19% to 29% with a 50% relative increase[1].
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12 The increased detection and removal of the adenomas may lead to increased benefits of
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15 screening on incidence and mortality of colorectal cancer[2].
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19 Despite the promising benefits of AI-aided detection, the new tools have
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22 downsides. AI-guided detection may increase polyp overdiagnosis and overtreatment.
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25 Of particular concern is the fact that current CADe tools mainly increase detection of
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28 small polyps, some of which are not neoplastic and thus do not need removal[3, 4].
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31 Increased detection of such polyps may increase patient burden, risk of complications,
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34 and costs by histopathological assessment of additional polyps unless the endoscopists
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37 are well experienced with optical diagnosis of polyps.
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41 Computer-aided diagnosis (CADx) tools for real-time diagnosis of polyp
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44 histology provides solution to overcome this challenge. Recent evidence suggests that
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47 CADx tools are expected to reduce the number of polyp removal by identifying non-
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50 neoplastic polyps[5]. However, further development of CADx tools is hampered by a
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53 critical challenge, namely unreliable pathological diagnoses. Development of CADx
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56 needs accurate pathological diagnoses of polyps which are used as gold standard
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1 diagnosis for machine learning[5]. However, these pathological diagnoses are subject to
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5 significant inter-observer variability among pathologists (Kappa coefficient ranges
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8 between 0.4 and 0.7[6-8]). This precludes a correct labelling of polyp images to feed the
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11 computer. Thus, it is difficult to create a reliable CADx system in colonoscopy because
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14 the performance of the developed CADx tools depends on the accuracy of the
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18 histopathological diagnosis.

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21 Technical developers of AI tools in colonoscopy are not aware of the challenges
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24 with their gold standard and take pathologists' diagnoses for face value. As more
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27 advanced, multi-class CADx tools will be developed, this problem will get worse.
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30 Actually, the multi-class CADx tools are expected to allow highly personalized medicine;
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33 a CADx tool which provides information on multi-class histology (e.g., non-neoplastic
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36 vs low-grade adenoma vs high-grade adenoma vs sessile serrated lesion vs invasive
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39 cancer) would help endoscopists pick up appropriate treatment options (non-removal,
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42 endoscopic treatment, or surgery) and predict surveillance interval even without taking
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45 any histological examination. Therefore, overcoming the above-mentioned challenge is
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48 prerequisite to improve the quality of colonoscopy practice with the aid of AI.
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53 Again, this hurdle for reliable development of CADx tools in colonoscopy is not
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56 widely recognized in the research community (to our knowledge, there has been no
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1 studies which elaborate on how to manage unreliable gold standards). Some may choose
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5 to sidestep this problem by discarding images with uncertain pathological diagnoses. But
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9 who decides what is uncertain? And any intentional selection of images for machine
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12 learning will reduce the generalizability of the developed CADx tools (a so-called
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15 overfitted model) and is thus not a promising way out.

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18 So, what is the solution? We suggest to use so-called semi-supervised learning
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21 when developing advanced CADx tools in medicine. Supervised learning is learning with
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24 labelled training data only with reliable histology of all polyps used, and unsupervised
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27 learning uses polyps with no requirement of reliably labelled polyp diagnosis. As the term
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30 indicates, semi-supervised learning for AI development includes both supervised and
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33 unsupervised learning[9]. The concept of semi-supervised learning is well suited in the
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36 discouraging situation we are facing where colonoscopy images cannot be labelled
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39 properly due to uncertain pathological diagnoses. With unsupervised learning, all images
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43 with uncertain diagnosis can be classified into meaningful clusters based on polyp
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46 appearance, instead of being taken away.

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49 Even though there are wide variations in pathological diagnoses, there are “true”,
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53 biologically unique features for each pathological polyp category (such as genetic
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57 features and potential to become malignant). For example, some study suggested that
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2 endoscopic appearance of sessile serrated lesions was closely associated with the extent
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5 of DNA methylation[10]. Recent evidence suggested these biological features might be
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8 equivalent to the morphological appearance of each polyp during colonoscopy.
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11 Endoscopic diagnosis of small polyps agreed by multiple expert endoscopists is closer to
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14 the true nature of the polyp than a single pathologist's diagnosis which is current clinical
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17 practice[11]. Another study also mentioned interobserver agreement among expert
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20 endoscopists was quite high (Kappa value of between 0.716 and 0.862) even for advanced
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24 lesions[12].
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28 Semi-supervised learning to develop reliable CADx tools for polyps in colorectal
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30 cancer screening involves the following steps:
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34 1) Two (or more) expert endoscopists review endoscopic images and
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37 corresponding pathological diagnosis of each polyp used in the training stages of the
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40 machine learning approach.
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44 2) When all evaluators agree on the preassigned pathological diagnosis of a lesion,
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47 the images are handled as the "labelled" data. if there is disagreement for preassigned
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50 pathological diagnosis, the pathological diagnosis is removed from the images. These
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53 images are handled as "unlabelled" data.
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58 3) In semi-supervised learning, unlabelled data are automatically classified into
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2 clusters with use of the information obtained from labelled data and similarity of the
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5 colonoscopy images between each data (**Figure 1**).
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9 Another possible solution is to improve the reliability of the gold standard, namely
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11 pathological diagnoses, with the aid of AI. A recent study showed that use of AI improved
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13 the accuracy of 4-class differentiation of pathological diagnoses from 74% to 81% [13].
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16 Combined utilisation of semi-supervised learning and AI-aided pathological diagnoses
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19 may be the best solution to overcome this problem.
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25 A limitation of our proposed approach is that it creates a “virtual” gold standard
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28 which is different from current standard histopathology. However, given the poor
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30 agreement amongst pathologists for polyp diagnosis, new disruptive methods are needed
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33 to develop advanced CADx tools in colonoscopy. The concept is also applicable to other
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36 cancer screening tests such as CADx for mammography and CADx for smear cytology,
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39 where the same problem applies in relation to variation in pathological diagnoses [14, 15].
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42 Our approach may help overcome the challenges of overdiagnosis and overtreatment
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45 induced by introduction of CADe tools in cancer screening, and will thus optimise cancer
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48 screening programs.
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References

- [1] Barua I, Vinsard DG, Jodal HC, Loberg M, Kalager M, Holme O, et al. Artificial intelligence for polyp detection during colonoscopy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Endoscopy*. 2021;53:277-84.
- [2] Mori Y, Bretthauer M, Kalager M. Hopes and Hypes for Artificial Intelligence in Colorectal Cancer Screening. *Gastroenterology*. 2021;161:774-7.
- [3] Wang P, Liu X, Berzin TM, Glissen Brown JR, Liu P, Zhou C, et al. Effect of a deep-learning computer-aided detection system on adenoma detection during colonoscopy (CADe-DB trial): a double-blind randomised study. *The lancet Gastroenterology & hepatology*. 2020;5:343-51.
- [4] Wang P, Berzin TM, Glissen Brown JR, Bharadwaj S, Becq A, Xiao X, et al. Real-time automatic detection system increases colonoscopic polyp and adenoma detection rates: a prospective randomised controlled study. *Gut*. 2019;68:1813-9.
- [5] Barua I, Wieszczy P, Kudo S, Misawa M, Holme Ø, Gulati S, et al. Real-Time AI-Based Optical Diagnosis of Neoplastic Polyps during Colonoscopy. *NEJM Evid*. In press.
- [6] Vennelaganti S, Cuatrecasas M, Vennalaganti P, Kennedy KF, Srinivasan S, Patil DT, et al. Interobserver Agreement Among Pathologists in the Differentiation of Sessile Serrated From Hyperplastic Polyps. *Gastroenterology*. 2021;160:452-4.e1.
- [7] Mollasharifi T, Ahadi M, Jamali E, Moradi A, Asghari P, Maroufizadeh S, et al. Interobserver Agreement in Assessing Dysplasia in Colorectal Adenomatous Polyps: A Multicentric Iranian Study. *Iranian journal of pathology*. 2020;15:167-74.
- [8] Lee M, Kudose S, Del Portillo A, Ko HM, Lee H, Pittman ME, et al. Invasive carcinoma versus pseudoinvasion: interobserver variability in the assessment of left-sided colorectal polypectomies. *J Clin Pathol*. 2021 (Accepted 31 March 2021) Online ahead of print.
- [9] Anand D, Yashashwi K, Kumar N, Rane S, Gann PH, Sethi A. Weakly supervised learning on unannotated H&E-stained slides predicts BRAF mutation in thyroid cancer with high accuracy. *The Journal of pathology*. 2021;255:232-42.
- [10] Kimura T, Yamamoto E, Yamano HO, Suzuki H, Kamimae S, Nojima M, et al. A novel pit pattern identifies the precursor of colorectal cancer derived from sessile serrated adenoma. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2012;107:460-9.
- [11] Ponugoti P, Rastogi A, Kaltenbach T, MacPhail ME, Sullivan AW, Thygesen JC, et al. Disagreement between high confidence endoscopic adenoma prediction and histopathological diagnosis in colonic lesions ≤ 3 mm in size. *Endoscopy*. 2019;51:221-6.

1 [12] Huang Q, Fukami N, Kashida H, Takeuchi T, Kogure E, Kurahashi T, et al. Interobserver
2 and intra-observer consistency in the endoscopic assessment of colonic pit patterns. *Gastrointest*
3 *Endosc.* 2004;60:520-6.
4
5

6 [13] Nasir-Moin M, Suriawinata AA, Ren B, Liu X, Robertson DJ, Bagchi S, et al. Evaluation of
7 an Artificial Intelligence-Augmented Digital System for Histologic Classification of Colorectal
8 Polyps. *JAMA network open.* 2021;4:e2135271.
9
10

11 [14] Stoler MH, Schiffman M. Interobserver reproducibility of cervical cytologic and histologic
12 interpretations: realistic estimates from the ASCUS-LSIL Triage Study. *Jama.* 2001;285:1500-5.
13
14

15 [15] van Seijen M, Jóźwiak K, Pinder SE, Hall A, Krishnamurthy S, Thomas JS, et al. Variability
16 in grading of ductal carcinoma in situ among an international group of pathologists. *The journal*
17 *of pathology Clinical research.* 2021;7:233-42.
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